

CELLULOSE NANOMATERIALS AND BASALT FIBRES: AN APPROACH TOWARDS LIGHT-WEIGHTING IN SHEET MOULDING COMPOUNDS

Amir Asadi¹, Ferdinand Baaij², Robert J. Moon³ and Kyriaki Kalaitzidou⁴

¹ G.W. Woodruff School of Mechanical Engineering – Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta, GA 30332, United States, amir.asadi@me.gatech.edu

² G.W. Woodruff School of Mechanical Engineering – Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta, GA 30332, United States, ferdinand.baaij@gatech.edu

³ The Forest Products Laboratory, U.S. Forest Service, Madison, Wisconsin 53726, United States and School of Materials Science and Engineering – Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta, GA 30332, United States, robertmoon@fs.fed.us

⁴ G.W. Woodruff School of Mechanical Engineering and School of Materials Science and Engineering – Georgia Institute of Technology, Atlanta, GA 30332, United States, kyriaki.kalaitzidou@me.gatech.edu

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on producing lighter sheet moulding compounds (SMC) composites by 1) replacing part of the heaviest component of SMC e.g. glass fibres (GF) with a small amount of cellulose nanomaterials and 2) using basalt fibres (BF) as an alternative to the traditionally used GF. In the first approach, it is found that adding 1 and 1.5 wt% cellulose nanocrystals (CNC) in the epoxy matrix of short GF/epoxy SMC composites allows removing 10 wt% of GF from typical SMC composites containing 35 wt% GF in epoxy, producing ~8% lighter composites with no compromise in tensile and flexural properties. The addition of 1 wt% CNC in 25GF/epoxy SMC composites results in increases of 15% in elastic modulus, 11% in flexural modulus and 14% in flexural strength, reaching the corresponding properties of 35GF/epoxy SMC composites. In the second approach, the feasibility of using BF as a replacement for GF in SMC composites was investigated. SMC composites with 25 wt% BF and 25 wt% GF are produced and compared in terms of fibre/matrix interfacial adhesion, cure behaviour and mechanical performance. The results show that both BF and GF have the same interfacial adhesion and curing behaviour. In addition, the tensile and flexural properties of BF SMC composites are higher or at least equal than those of GF SMC composites. The results to date indicate that replacing part of GF with CNC or substituting GF with BF can lead to lightweight SMC composites without any compromise of the properties compared to the state of the art GF/epoxy SMC.

1 INTRODUCTION

The fuel economy in vehicles can be increased using lighter vehicles as 10% reduction in the vehicle weight can result in 6-8 % increase in fuel efficiency [1]. One approach toward light weighting is using glass/carbon fibre reinforced polymer composites. Sheet moulding compounds (SMC), which consist of short glass fibres (GF) impregnated between two layers of thermoset resin are the precursor GFRP for automotive applications allowing for high volume production and part reproducibility with high specific strength and stiffness, and desired surface finish in a cost effective way.

One solution towards reducing the weight of composites is to replace the heaviest component with a lighter but stronger material [2], e.g. nanomaterials [3]. The major challenges are inhomogeneous dispersion and agglomeration, thermal stability and lack of scalable ways to introduce nanomaterials in SMC manufacturing. Cellulose nanomaterials (CN) have a high potential to be used as polymer reinforcement due to their attractive properties such as low density (1.6 g/cm³), high aspect ratio (10-100) and surface area, tensile strength of ~3GPa, elastic modulus of 110-220 GPa, surfaces with accessible hydroxyl side groups that can be readily chemically modified and their low toxicity [4]. Current methods of addition of CNC in the polymer composites, i.e. use of waterborne epoxies [5],

solvent exchange methods [6], CN preforms [7] or chemical modification of CN surfaces [8] are both time inefficient and costly and thus limited for scale up in production of SMC composites. In this study, cellulose nanocrystals, CNC, which are whisker shaped particles (3–20 nm in width and 50–500 nm in length) was used with properties in the range listed above.

In the first part of this study, we explore whether it is possible to reduce the weight of a typical 35 wt% GF/epoxy SMC composite by replacing part of the GF with CNC without compromising the mechanical performance. According to our prior work, addition of CNC up to 0.9 wt% in the SMC composites improved the mechanical properties of the 35GF/epoxy composites [9]. The effect of adding 1 and 1.5 wt% CNC into the resin on mechanical properties of the 25GF/CNC-epoxy SMC composites is investigated. 35GF/epoxy SMC composite with no CNC is used as a reference.

An alternative approach to reducing the weight of composites is replacing GF with a smaller amount of a stronger material. The feasibility of using Basalt fibres (BF) instead of GF in SMC composites was explored. Basalt, usually black or grey in colour and formed by the rapid cooling of basalt lava, is one of the most common rocks on earth. Although the manufacturing process of BF is similar to that of GF, i.e. fibre drawing or spinning, no additives are required in BF manufacturing as pure basalt rock is the only raw material for fibre production [10]. Characteristics such as high strength, modulus and elongation at break, chemical and thermal stability (in the range of -200 to 600-800 °C), sound thermal insulation, resistance to most weather conditions, easy processability, eco-friendly and low cost [11, 12] make BF an attractive alternative to GF and carbon fibres. BF have been used either as a single reinforcement [13] or along with other reinforcements, e.g. micro-reinforcement [14] and nano-reinforcements [15], in both thermoset and thermoplastic polymer composites. In addition, based on BF vs GF comparative studies BF composites exhibit a relatively better or equal performance to GF [12, 16]. The effect of fibre type, i.e. GF and BF, on the interfacial adhesion between fibre/matrix, the curing behaviour and mechanical performance of the BF/epoxy SMC composites are determined and compared with those of GF/epoxy SMC composites.

2 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1 Materials and fabrication

Multi end roving GF ME1510 (TEX 4800, single filament diameter of $10\pm 1\ \mu\text{m}$) were received from Owens Corning (Oak Brook, IL, US) and multi end roving BF (TEX 4800, single filament diameter of $10\pm 1\ \mu\text{m}$) were provided by Mafic Ireland (Kells, County Meath, Ireland). Both BF and GF were used in the manufacturing of the SMC as received. A bicomponent epoxy resin consisting of 150 thick epoxy (diglycidyl ether of Bisphenol-A epoxy) and 556 slow polyamide hardener supplied by US Composites (Wes Palm Beach, FL) was used. Aerosil-Cabosil (fumed silica) supplied by US composites was also used as thickening agent. CNC in the form of freeze-dried were supplied by the USDA Forest Service-Forest Products Laboratory (FPL), Madison, WI, USA.

The resin used in the SMC production of GF/CNC-epoxy composites was prepared in a two-step process: i) dispersion of the CNC in the hardener using sonication, and ii) mixing the CNC-hardener suspension with the epoxy. The desired amount of CNC (1.4 and 2 wt% in the resin) was stirred with 500 g hardener and then sonicated (UIP500hd heilscher ultrasonic processor, 34 mm probe diameter, amplitude of 90) for 20 and 30 min depending on the CNC content, with longer time for the higher concentration determined by visual inspection. Next, 60 g fumed silica thickening agent was mixed with the hardener-CNC suspension by manual stirring for 10 min at room temperature. Finally, 1000 g epoxy was added to the hardener-CNC-fumed silica mixture and manually stirred for 5 min. The ratio of the epoxy to hardener was 2:1 wt% as proposed by the supplier. The final concentration of the thickening agent in the resin was 4 wt%. Resins with CNC concentrations of 0, 1.4 and 2 wt% were prepared using the above procedure. The resin for comparing GF and BF containing SMC composites were prepared in a similar way described above but with no CNC.

GF/epoxy SMC composites contained 25 wt% GF and 35 wt% GF and BF/epoxy SMC composites had 25 wt% fibre content. CNC were added to the SMC composite with 25 wt% GF. The SMC line used was manufactured by Finn and Fram. The plates containing three SMC layers stacked on top of one another and hot pressed using a Carver 4122 manual heated press at 124 kPa and 100 °C for 1 h,

followed by post-curing at 120 °C for 2 h. After curing, the plates remained at room temperature for 48 h prior to cutting and testing to prevent any potential plastic deformation during handling/testing. The dimensions of the final plates were 304×267×5 mm³. Test coupons were cut from the plates using a waterjet (MAXIEM 1515). The naming scheme for the GF/epoxy and BF/epoxy SMC composites is 35GF/epoxy, 25GF/*n*CNC-epoxy, where *n* is the CNC wt% in the composite, and 25BF/epoxy.

2.1 Characterization techniques

Single fibre fragmentation (SFF) tests, as described by Hunston et al. , were used to determine the effect of fibre type, i.e. GF and BF, on the interfacial shear strength (IFSS) [17]. For SFF test specimen preparation, individual ~120 mm long filament GF (BF) filaments were carefully pulled off from the corresponding rovings and placed in the middle of a dogbone shaped mould with a gauge length of 25 mm long, width of 3 mm and a depth of 2 mm, an overall length and width of 80 and 10 mm, respectively. No fumed silica was used in SFF samples to keep the transparency of the cured samples for measuring the fibre fragments under the optical microscope (Leica DM2500 polarized light optical microscope). Then, tensile tests using an Instron 33R 4466 equipped with a 500 N load cell were carried out for SFF samples at a displacement rate of 1 mm/min and input to the Tyson-Kelly equation, given in eq. (1), to determine IFSS values for BF/epoxy and GF/epoxy SMC composites.

$$\tau_i = \frac{d_f \sigma_f(l_c)}{2l_c} = \frac{3d_f \sigma_f(l_c)}{8\bar{l}} \quad (1)$$

The GF fibre strength was estimated by tensile testing (ASTM D3822) where a single GF fibre was attached to a paper tab with a gauge length of 25.4 mm and tested at a displacement rate of 1 mm/min. Both IFSS and single fibre strength values are the average of at least seven samples.

Water displacement method was used to measure the specific density of the SMC composites according to ASTM D-792. Each density data point is an average of at least 12 measurements. A

The tensile properties of the composites were determined according to ASTM D638 using an Instron 33R 4466 equipped with 10 kN load cell for dog bone samples with a gauge length of 57 mm, width of 13.1mm and thickness of 5mm. An extensometer, Instron 2630-106, with a gauge length of 25 mm was used to record the axial strain. The flexural properties were measured using three-point bending tests with the same Instron according to ASTM D790-02 with a support span of 50 mm and thickness of 5 mm at a displacement rate of 2.15 mm/min. Each tensile and flexural data point is an average of at least 10 tests. The impact energy was measured according to ISO179 using Charpy tests with an Instron SI series pendulum impact tester with a maximum impact head of 406.7 J with a support span of 43 mm for 12.7 mm wide and ~5 mm thick rectangular samples. Each data point is an average of at least 12 tests

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Interfacial properties

Table 1 presents the average fiber critical length (= 4/3 of the average fibre fragment lengths) and the calculated IFSS, as a function of the fibre type. i.e. GF and BF. As the results imply, the IFSS for both types of fibre are similar suggesting similar interfacial properties in the two types of composites. The average strength values for GF and BF were measured as 4.1±0.7 and 4.4±0.7 GPa respectively. Weibull distribution was applied for the fibre strength data [18] to obtain the Weibull modulus as 4.13 and 4.79 for GF and BF respectively. Although the fumed silica was not added to SFF samples, it is expected that the possible change in IFSS due to addition of fumed silica to be the same in both types of SMC composites.

Material	IFSS (MPa)	Critical length(μm)
25GF/epoxy	39.8 \pm 8	758.1 \pm 98
25BF/epoxy	42.7 \pm 6	729.7 \pm 62

Table 1: Interfacial shear strength (IFSS) and average fragmentation length for GF/epoxy and BF/epoxy composites.

3.2 Specific density

The measured density for 35GF/epoxy, 25GF/CNC-epoxy and 25BF/epoxy SMC composites are shown in Table 2. The average measured density of 25BF/epoxy composites was 3% higher than that of 25GF/epoxy composites which was expected due to the higher density of BF (2.75 g/cm³) compared to that of GF (2.55 g/cm³). Also, addition of CNC in the composite did not affect the density as expected.

Material	ρ_{exp} (g/cm ³)	$\rho_{theoretical}$ (g/cm ³)
25GF/epoxy	1.33 \pm 0.02 (1.25 \pm 0.01)*	1.33
25GF/1CNC-epoxy	1.33 \pm 0.02	1.32
25GF/1.5CNC-epoxy	1.33 \pm 0.02	1.32
35GF/epoxy	1.43 \pm 0.05	1.42
25BF/epoxy	1.29 \pm 0.04*	1.34

Table 2: Density for GF/epoxy and BF/epoxy composites.

* A separate set of experiments

3.2 Curing behaviour

The effect of fibre type and CNC on the overall curing behaviour and formation of the epoxy network determined using DSC is shown in Table 2. CNC content of up to 1.4% with respect to the epoxy resin did not impact the curing temperature and time of the CNC-epoxy, both determined at the exothermic peak. However, the maximum heat flow and the heat of reaction (the area under the heat flow curve for the used epoxy resin in each sample) slightly decreased with increase in the CNC content because of restriction imposed by CNC presence in network formation. The fibre type, i.e. GF or BF, did not impact the curing temperature and time as well as the maximum heat flow and the heat of reaction considering the statistical deviation. However, addition of fibre increased the cure time and temperature compared to those of neat epoxy.

Sample	Max. heat flow (W/g- epoxy)	Heat of reaction (ΔH , J/g- epoxy)	Cure temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Cure time (min)
0CNC-epoxy	1.04 \pm 0.1	418.6 \pm 16	106.3 \pm 2	8 \pm 0.3
1.4CNC-epoxy	1.01 \pm 0.1	399.3 \pm 4	105.6 \pm 0.8	8 \pm 0.2
GF/epoxy	0.77 \pm 0.1	548.6 \pm 35	94.4 \pm 1.4	14 \pm 0.3
BF/Epoxy	0.81 \pm 0.1	556.7 \pm 29	94.4 \pm 0.3	14 \pm 0.1

Table 3: Effect of fibre type and CNC on the cure characteristics of the epoxy resin

3.3 Mechanic properties

The effect of the CNC content and fibre type on the tensile and flexural properties of SMC composites is presented in Fig. 1. Introducing 1 and 1.5 wt% CNC (equivalent to 1.4 and 2 wt% CNC in epoxy) in 25GF/CNC-epoxy SMC composites enhanced the elastic modulus by ~15% reaching the level of 35GF/epoxy SMC composites and reduced the density by 8% with regards to that of 35GF/epoxy SMC composites. The tensile strength and elongation at break of all the SMC composites with and without CNC was in the same range. The strength of the SMC composites containing CNC, i.e. 25GF/CNC-epoxy, did not decrease. Similar trends to those observed for the tensile properties are also seen in the flexural properties shown in Fig. 1 where the flexural modulus in 25GF/CNC-epoxy SMC composites enhanced by ~11% respectively compared to 25GF/epoxy SMC composites reaching that of the SMC composites with 35 wt% GF. In addition, the strength of 25GF/1.5CNC-epoxy SMC composites improved by ~14% increased to the level of 35GF/epoxy composites. No significant statistical change in the flexural strains at break was observed for the SMC composites with different GF and CNC contents.

The average tensile and flexural moduli of 25BF/epoxy SMC composites were higher by 13% and 15% respectively with respect to those of 25GF/epoxy SMC composites despite the overlapped statistical standard deviation of the experimental data. The specific tensile and flexural moduli (modulus divided by density) shows the same trend where they are both 10% higher for 25BF/epoxy with respect to those of 25GF/epoxy SMC composites, as presented in Table 4, due to the higher modulus of BF (87 GPa) compared to that of GF (75 GPa). The differences between the strength values (absolute and specific) of the two composites are not statistically significant.

The impact strength for all type of composites are plotted in Fig. 2. Addition of CNC did not statistically alter the impact energy of the 25GF/CNC-epoxy SMC. However, the impact energy of SMC composites decreased by 22% because of removing of 10 wt% GF. To offset this drop in impact energy, it is possible to add elastomers to the resin or increase the glass fibre length.

The impact strength of 25BF/epoxy is similar to that of 25GF/epoxy composites taking into account the coinciding standard deviation as shown in Fig. 2. Similar trend is observed for specific impact strength of both composites as shown in Table 4.

Overall, adding a small amount of CNC, i.e. 1 and 1.5 wt%, in the 25GF/CNC-epoxy SMC composites enhanced the tensile and flexural properties to the level of 35GF/epoxy composites, resulting in a 8% lighter composite with no compromise in tensile and flexural properties. However, the impact energy of the composites was compromised due to removing of part of glass fibres. In addition, using BF instead of GF in SMC composites provide improved or at least equal mechanical properties suggesting BF as an alternative to GF in SMC products.

Figure 1: Effect of the CNC content and fibre type on tensile and flexural properties of SMC composites. Error bars are 1 standard deviation.

Figure 2: Effect of the CNC content and fibre type on impact strength of SMC composites. Error bars are 1 standard deviation.

Sample	Specific tensile modulus (GPa)*	Specific tensile strength (MPa)*	Specific flexural modulus (GPa)*	Specific flexural strength (MPa)*	Specific impact strength (kJ/m ²)
25GF/epoxy	4.9±0.8	57.4±7.8	4.2±0.3	103.9±10.1	53.3±8.4
25BF/Epoxy	5.4±1.2	50.5±15.4	4.7±0.8	105.9±19.9	48.1±10

Table 4: Specific tensile and flexural properties of 25GF/epoxy and 25BF/epoxy SMC composites.

* All the values are normalized over density (g/cm³)

4 CONCLUSIONS

A small amount of CNC, i.e. 1 and 1.5 wt%, in epoxy resin allowed removing 10 wt% GF from SMC composites producing 8% lighter composites without any reduction in tensile and flexural properties. Incorporation of 1 and 1.5 wt% CNC in 25GF/CNC-epoxy SMC composites enhanced the tensile and flexural modulus by ~15% and ~11% respectively and flexural strength by 14% 25GF/CNC-epoxy SMC composites reaching to the level of 35GF/epoxy SMC composites with no CNC. Taking out 10 wt% GF reduced the impact energy by 22%.

In addition, BF were used in SMC manufacturing as an alternative to GF and the two composites were compared in terms of their properties. The interfacial adhesion of both composites was similar leading to similar stress transfer ability across the fibre/matrix interphase. Tensile, flexural, impact (absolute and specific) values were coinciding for both types of composites. The results of this study highlight the possibility of using CNC and BF in SMC manufacturing leading to producing lighter composites with enhanced properties.

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